

IoT Services Applied at the Smart Cities Level

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Abstract. The Internet of Things (IoT) can consolidate transparently and seamlessly diverse or heterogeneous end systems by granting open access to chosen subsets of data for the development of an excessive amount of digital services. Forming a general architecture for the IoT is indeed a very challenging task, mainly because of the type of devices, link layer technologies, and services that may concern in such a system. IoT visualizes to connect billions of sensors to the Internet to utilize them for practical and productive resource management in Smart Cities. Today, infrastructure platforms and software applications administered as services using cloud technologies. An immense pressure towards organized city management has triggered many Smart City ambitions by both government and private sector businesses to finance in information and communication technologies and to find sustainable solutions to the increasing issues. This paper will be focused on the Smart Services Platform developed through the CitiSim project. Its main objective is to help in providing services for making city life better for the citizens. Also, it was designed to give users powerful monitoring and control infrastructure and to enable them to make critical management decisions on the information provided by the platform.

Keywords: IoT · Smart services platform · Critical management decision

1 Introduction

Over the last decades, urban populations have faced a rapid rise that leads to lots of changes in the global infrastructure. In our modern days, the cities have expanded along with the evolution of technology, and they developed the need for integrating information and communication technologies to evaluate what is happening. With these technologies and the integrated sensors, the management of the cities can monitor in real-time the systems and make better decisions regarding the security, the water supply, the traffic, lighting systems, parking lots, among others.

The concept of smart cities promotes the increase in the quality and the performance of the urban services, using communication and information technologies based on the IoT, among others, bringing a significant impact on the solutions for the modern cities. However, due to the variety of possibilities when choosing the devices and services involved, creating an IoT architecture can become a somewhat convoluted

task. This way, the future of the smart cities will be improved starting from safety, lighting, security, traffic, and parking to the citizens' engagement and the management of the cities [1].

One of the essential aspects in smart cities is mobility - smart traffic lights systems, intelligent parking, smart grid, and multi-modal transportation, helping to reduce congestion, diminishing the time of looking for a parking spot, monitoring the traffic flow, and offering citizens the possibility of checking in real-time information about the public transportation. Also, buildings that monitor their usage of energy are more economical, since they report the collected and analyzed data. The rest of the paper is organized as following: Sect. 2 analyzes related work, Sect. 3 presents the CitiSim platform, while Sect. 4 details the IoT-based smart services, Sect. 5 draws the conclusions and outlines future work.

2 Related Work

The main component in smart cities that brings everything together is the IoT and the devices it comes with: sensors and beacons, which are essential in this context. All the information in a smart city is collected from deployed sensors is then sent to a complex system with the purpose of creating real-time management. Because too much data can be sometimes overwhelming, beacons come in the help of smart cities, primarily since they represent a lower cost solution also. In this sense, cities can deploy a private network of beacons to collect and transmit the information to an integrated hub [2]. Some implemented IoT solutions for Smart Cities are the following platforms described below.

AirCasting is an open-source platform used for recording, mapping, and sharing environmental and health data through the citizens' smartphones. Each new AirCasting session comes with the chance of capturing real-world measurements, define and document the received data. Through the mobile app of AirCasting, the users can record, map, and share the following [3]: sound levels, humidity, temperature, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), fine particle matter (PM_{2.5}) concentrations, breathing rate, heart rate, and heart rate variability, activity level measurements.

Another solution for smart cities is Bigbelly - an easy-access and secure to hide in plain sight platform that delivers smart recycling and waste solutions. Besides giving an update to the city services, used for hosting supplementary technologies. This web-based, cloud-connected solution transmits insights data about the waste operations of the citizens. Bigbelly comes with a variety of services all combined under a compact model that captures information from the high-traffic areas, besides the less hectic ones. This integrated platform comes as a customizable turnkey solution with an increased capacity that can deploy from the users' platform [4].

An important field of Smart City platforms is represented by monitoring the environmental factors, such as air quality, humidity, sun exposure etc. [5]. For this purpose, one of the most advanced trackers used for the environment is TZOA, a solution that uses internal sensors that measure some parameters like temperature, air quality, humidity, ambient light, atmospheric pressure and UV exposure from the sun, all included in one compact wearable device. It can be connected to the user's

smartphone so that it can help in the decision-making process since it displays in real-time a map of the environmental data. The air quality sensor presents concentrations, counts the number of individual particles, and identifies allergens, and different pollution indexes. The information is streamed onto the smartphone application, then sent in the cloud with the purpose of creating a map that is available to all the users. Moreover, the TZOA app sends actionable recommendations like choosing less polluted paths, opening the windows to refresh the air or making sure the users get the right amount of sunshine during seasons [6].

Another solution implemented in Smart Cities is Smart City Map, which is an online multifunctional data hub accessed from a mobile application. This solution was built as a customizable multilevel map, working with big data in real-time. Also, it provides localized information with the help of “CityDataPub” - a digital infrastructure, and it can also send incident reports directly. The features it comes with are: free Wi-Fi, city tourism, accessibility (helps the user can search and discover points of interest), local recycle (displays the nearest recycling centers and exchange centers using geolocation), incident report [7].

Traffic optimization is essential for Smart City platforms. In this regard, Current designed and developed an IoT platform called CityIQ [8] which provides opportunities for traffic optimization, bicycle flows optimization, safety and convenience optimization for citizens and parking improvement. This open platform is based on IoT devices mounted on lamp-post nodes for the provision of data. Using the GUI, the data can be visualized in near real time and is available via APIs to a client ecosystem.

In the concept of Smart Cities, important roles are played by Big Data, for processing data collected through IoT devices and Cloud Computing, for reduced costs and reliability of services [9]. Huawei developed an open ecosystem called OceanConnect [10], which provides over 170 APIs for the development of Smart City services in the area of smart homes, smart utilities metering, smart parking and safe city [11]. The platform provides support for a wide range of protocols, such as Z-Wave, ZigBee and Wi-Fi, TCP, UDP, MQTT, CoAP and LWM2M. Hitachi Vantara by Hitachi [12] is another Smart City solution enabled by IoT, Big Data, analytics and video intelligence, which addresses two main areas: Smart Spaces [13], and Public Safety and Security [14]. Smart Spaces integrates data collected from IoT sensors with data provided by video cameras, social media and other sources to support public safety and security, traffic and mobility, airports and ports, campuses and retailers. The Public Safety and Security service solution generates automated alerts using data from video cameras, CAD systems, gunshot detectors, facial readers and license plate readers to provide automated alerts for intrusions, object detection and facial recognition.

A Smart City environment entails the use of very diverse devices. Impact is an IoT platform developed by Nokia which connects various devices and enables the management of a wide array of IP based protocols and non-IP based Low Power WAN protocols, including NB-IoT and LoRa [15, 16]. The platform’s main features include: auto detection and identification of subscriber devices, automation of remote provisioning, remote update and repair of device configurations, large-scale or bulk management actions, management of device faults and multi-domain/multi-protocol device management.

3 CitiSim – Platform for Smart Cities Solutions

CitiSim is a smart services platform developed within the project with the same name.

The main objective of this platform is to provide a reliable monitoring and control infrastructure that can take decisions in critical situations, based on the information provided by the platform components and gathered data.

The structure of the architecture consists of four layers as follows:

- **IoT Layer** - All data from the sensors are collected here. The sensors are registered in the message broker through an interface as publisher and each sensor call message broker interface periodically with its value and some metadata about the reading (e.g., Expiring time, Timestamp, quality of the reading etc.);
- **Core Layer** - It represents the platform itself. The main components of this layer are:
 - **Message Broker:** It's used for raw data, events and sensor information;
 - **Filter Service:** This service is defined in order to allow users to subscribe to a specific topic;
 - **Property Service:** This is a service devoted to storing static/semi-static properties of devices/services in an instance of the platform, like the position of a smoke sensor, the last revision of an extincitor, the manufacturer of specific actuators are examples of information stored/accessed through the property service;
 - **Persistent Service:** This service is subscribed to all topics in the message broker and store, in the data store;
 - **Semantic KB:** This knowledge database will store basically three types of information: the vocabulary and relations of concepts in a current city, the rules about how a city works regarding traffic and pedestrian and a service description of the instances running in this instance of CitiSim;
 - **Scheduling Service:** This experimental service will orchestrate complex behaviors according to the services deployed and a new desire expressed by a user or service. For example, the opening of a door to go into a building can be done by several methods (facial recognition, RFID tag, PIN code etc.) according to the TIC infrastructure deployed;
 - **Semantic Service:** This service will manage information at semantic level and it will integrate other domains with Smart Cities domain;
 - **Manager Tool:** Used for monitoring the platform and the state of the services and devices;
 - **Adapters:** These modules interconnect CitiSim with other domains (e.g., MQTT devices, Kafka based platforms, Sofia2 services etc.).
- **Urban modeling layer:** This layer will store structural information about the city (urban furniture, street layout, 3D buildings models, supplies models);
- **Smart service layer:** This layer takes the information collected in the core layer and by using the urban model layer provides a service related to stakeholders of a smart city. Here are defined and implemented the following smart services: Pollution, Energy and Infrastructure monitoring service, People and Traffic monitoring, Emergency service, Citizen Reporting, Semantic Search Service and Visual Wiki.

4 IoT-Based Smart Services

Two IoT-based smart services developed using the CitiSim framework are the Smart Energy Business Intelligence and the Environmental Motion Assistant. Both solutions are based on IoT networks that collect data in real time using urban and extra urban sensors.

The Smart Energy Business Intelligence service facilitates the substantiation of decisions to invest in green energy production based on consumption patterns identified by collecting data from the building using energy and environmental sensors [17].

Figure 1 depicts the architecture of the Smart Energy Business Intelligence platform, which is based on three main layers: IoT services layer, the back-end and the front-end.

Fig. 1. Smart energy business intelligence platform architecture

A wide range of sensors from providers as Verbund, Siemens, Fibaro and Libelium are being used to collect real-time data from different cost centres. Using the CitiSim Subscriber Service that retrieves data from the CitiSim Data Broker, the data is sent to the back-end which follows a REST architecture based on Python Flask Rest services for data processing, and then to the front-end where it can be visualized by the user.

The Environmental Motion Assistant (E.M.A.) was developed as a service that should help any potential user to have a clear understanding of the surrounding environment, while being specifically designed for closed mobile contexts, like for example the interior of a vehicle. The service and its associated device are not limited to interior conditions, the user having the possibility to use it outdoors, in various situations like for example when riding a bike or taking a walk. By using E.M.A., as a Smart Mobility Service, environmental and motion parameters (CO₂, alcohol concentration, temperature, humidity, air quality, dust, speed, accelerations, rotations etc.) are continuously measured and stored for any user context, insightful visualizations being provided through a mobile and a web application.

As depicted in Fig. 2, there are several components integrated into E.M.A.: (a) sensor pack, which is a prototyped device containing necessary sensors, (b) a database that stores the data generated by the devices, (c) a data collector machine

where the REST API is deployed, (d) an API that is used to collect the data coming from various sources, (e) the CitiSim Data Broker used for data integration and (f) a graphical user interface for user visualizations and interactions with the platform.

Fig. 2. Environmental motion assistant platform architecture

The REST service can be considered the integration core of the platform, as it is used for all important data operations: 1) getting data from the devices, 2) serving data to web application, 3) serving data to mobile application.

5 Conclusions

CitiSim is the ideal solution when it comes to smart city platforms because it supports the development and simulation of intelligent services within a common framework. In order to demonstrate the usefulness of the platform and the services it offers, more applications will be implemented in the field of smart energy, smart mobility, and smart emergency. Smart City is on the rise and has a huge impact on the economy of the modern world. The benefits of CitiSim's exploitation are to the society represented by citizens and the economy, in terms of market values. The major innovation of CitiSim is that it wishes to provide the first Smart City-specific platform to monitor in real time, and in 2D/3D a large infrastructure of the city and that enables to interact with users by developing or testing added-value and customized services in an agile, simple way. As future work we envision to perform experiments on live data from cities.

Acknowledgment. This work has been supported in part by UEFISCDI Romania and MCI through projects CitiSim, PARFAIT and VLC/IR-RF, funded in part by European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 826452 (Arrowhead Tools), No. 787002 (SAFECARE), No. 777996 (SealedGRID) and No. 872698 (HUBCAP).

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